

THE STUDY OF COMMUNICATION AND TRANSLATION
STRATEGIES

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Annotation: *The main components of the strategy include situation orientation, goal formulation, forecasting, and planning. The more developed the cognitive scheme of translation, that is, the more different situational and operational “scenarios” of verbal-cognitive strategies are encoded in it, the higher the level of strategy formation, the more opportunities the translator has to organize his activities correctly.*

Key words: *Strategy, translation process, nature and sequence of actions in the translation process, self-organization.*

In the light of activity-based approaches to modeling the translation process, the study of the concept of “translation strategy” is of particular importance. The initial postulates of the translation strategy are largely determined by the intermediary role of the translator; the translator's activity only makes sense when it meets the expectations of participants in cross-language communication. The overall strategy of the translator is based on the desire to understand the translated text as fully as possible and find the most accurate match in the translation language. In this regard, V.N. Komissarov notes that the most important strategic principles of an interpreter include a critical attitude to their actions and maximum efforts to find the best option.

Strategy is considered as an activity category, a way of self-organization of the individual in the process of activity, a function of the subject. Researchers refer

to the characteristics of the translator's personality as communication skills: the ability to navigate in the context of communication, plan your speech correctly, choose the content of communication, find adequate means to convey thoughts and provide feedback. In the cognitive scheme of translation, researchers distinguish three interrelated levels: cognitive schemes of speech types that are part of translation as a receptive and productive speech activity; normative translation models (knowledge that forms the theoretical basis for the formation of translation skills); adaptive translation models that develop in the subject of activity in accordance with his individual style [1]. The essence of the translation strategy is to plan future activities, prepare them for specific conditions and in accordance with a specific goal. [1].

It is possible to define a translation strategy as a non-finite set of professional, effective, dynamic, logically interrelated, consistent universal and individual techniques. These techniques are purposefully used in the process of translation activities in a bilingual situation to optimize the understanding of the source text and flexible variable search for the most accurate match to the source text in the translation language, taking into account the conditions of translation, the type of text and the nature of the intended recipient. The translation strategy is systemic in nature, characterized by reference to the individual's mental processes and the translator's critical attitude to the actions performed. The relation of the translation strategy to mental processes, the dependence of the strategy on the subject, and the awareness / unconsciousness of its use allow us to consider the set of strategies used by the translator as individual, and the list of possible translation strategies as open.

Within the framework of the model, detailed characteristics of diplomatic, political, legal, and mass-information discourses are presented, the main features and strategies for translating relevant texts are formulated in various types of institutional discourse are considered, and the possibilities of using the model in teaching consecutive oral translation and in preparing for conference translation

are considered. It is necessary to detail the provisions of the author's discursive and communicative translation model based on the analysis of traditional and modern translation models, patterns and trends in modeling the translation process, which allows us to present a holistic concept of the discursive and communicative approach to translation. Systematization of the basic principles of modeling the translation process in the framework of the study allows us to identify the essential characteristics of the modeling process, consider traditional and modern interpretations of the concepts of "translation model", "translation strategy" and clarify their content, expand theoretical knowledge in the field of translation studies, translation didactics.

Comparative analysis of traditional translation models and modern approaches, systematization of interdisciplinary approaches to modeling the translation process and the obtained detailed characteristics of various translation models allow us to develop the theoretical and methodological foundations of an integral approach to modeling the translation process, which opens up new directions in translation studies, the study of discourse, text, communication, and the study of translation strategy. The results of the study form the basis of recommendations for professional translators to analyze the features and identify strategies for translating texts of various genres and topics in various language combinations. It is possible to consider the results of the study as a contribution to the development of interdisciplinary directions in the study of the translation process, expanding the theoretical base for modeling the translation process and building philological models.

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